

Canopy height Mapper: A google earth engine application for predicting global canopy heights combining GEDI with multi-source data

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ABSTRACT

Spatially and temporally discontinuous canopy height footprints collected by NASA's GEDI (Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation) mission are accessible on the Google Earth Engine (GEE) cloud computing platform. This study introduces an open-source, user-friendly, code-free GEE web application called Canopy Height Mapper (CH-GEE), available at <https://ee-calvites1990.projects.earthengine.app/view/ch-gee>, which automatically generates (10 m) high-resolution canopy height maps for a specific area by integrating GEDI with multi-source remote sensing data: Copernicus and topographical data from the GEE data catalogue. CH-GEE generates local-to-country scale calibrated canopy height maps worldwide using machine learning algorithms and leveraging the GEE platform's big data and cloud computing capabilities. CH-GEE allows customization of geographic area, algorithms and time windows for GEDI and predictors. Canopy heights generated by CH-GEE were validated using the Italian National Forest Inventory across 110,000 km² at multiple scales (Country-based R-squared = 0.89, RMSE = 17%). CH-GEE's accuracy and scalability make it suitable for forest monitoring.

1. Introduction

Climate change exacerbates global forest disturbances, due to an increasing frequency of extreme meteorological conditions such as drought, wildfire, and severe storms. Unstable environmental conditions alter successional processes, restoration attempts (Caron et al., 2021), carbon sequestration capacities (Heinrich et al., 2021) and increase plant mortality (Ma et al., 2023). Forest disturbance subsequently affect ecological functions, by limiting the quantity and quality of habitats available to species, thus negatively impacting biodiversity (Hall et al., 2011). Forest canopy structure has emerged as a crucial factor in

accurately assessing and monitoring forest condition in a changing climate. Specifically, canopy height dynamics is significant for quantifying carbon stocks (Heinrich et al., 2021; Jucker et al., 2017), because canopy height and diameter at breast height (DBH) are key parameters for evaluating tree growth dynamics (Sharma et al., 2019; Tabacchi et al., 2011). Canopy structural variation has been used to monitor biodiversity because structurally diverse canopies provide a wider range of habitats for species (Cazzolla Gatti et al., 2017; Kreft and Jetz, 2007; Marselis et al., 2020). The occurrence of canopy gaps is a normal ecosystem process, however an increase in gap size or frequency associated with direct and indirect human induced forest disturbance

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(Dalagnol et al., 2021). Lastly, identifying the tallest/lowest canopy heights can enhance the management of vulnerable or endangered species in protected areas (Ceccherini et al., 2023).

Therefore, periodic global canopy monitoring is crucial for tracking the carbon pool, biodiversity, and plant growth and assessing the health status of terrestrial ecosystems worldwide. These data are essential for determining ecological resilience and ecosystem restoration as well as facilitating sustainable management (Lisella et al., 2022; Canadell and Raupach, 2008; Hutchison et al., 2018; Nabuurs et al., 2019). A comprehensive understanding of canopy structural patterns and changes over time can also contribute to achieving the goals of the Paris Agreement (Schleussner et al., 2016) and the Sustainable Development Goals outlined in the UN's 2030 Agenda (Herold et al., 2019). Currently, canopy height data are periodically collected through National Forest Inventory (NFI) programs, but this varies significantly from country to country (Gasparini et al., 2022; Tomppo et al., 2008). Some countries conduct aerial laser scanning (ALS) campaigns, providing high-resolution wall-to-wall canopy height model (CHM) maps, but their coverage is often limited to a few hundred hectares (Alvites et al., 2022; D'Amico et al., 2021). While the NFI surveys offer comprehensive information on forest ecosystems nationally, field activities are expensive, time-consuming, and require trained staff (Brienen et al., 2015; West, 2009).

In this context, satellite data has become crucial for periodic, detailed, and accurate remotely sensed monitoring of vegetation conditions (Alvites et al., 2021, 2022; Francini et al., 2023a; Liang et al., 2019; Vangi et al., 2023). Several NASA missions, including ICESat-2 (Ice, Cloud and Land Elevation Satellite) and GEDI (Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation), have focused on the extensive canopy height monitoring from space, facilitating global studies on biomass and vegetation patterns (Dubayah, 2021; Liu et al., 2021). Since late 2018, NASA's GEDI mission has been monitoring 3D canopy structures between 51.6°S and 51.6°N using a complete waveform lidar instrument (Dubayah, 2021). GEDI's Level 2 A product includes 100 relative canopy height measurements (1–100 Rh percentile) with a spatial resolution of 25 m. GEDI footprints are spaced approximately 60 m apart along the satellite's track and roughly 600 m across the track (Dubayah, 2021). While some studies have utilized GEDI-L2 data to explore global patterns of vegetation structure, the large footprint size and discontinuous nature of these data poses challenges for monitoring entire forest and non-forest extents, particularly at local and regional scales (Lahssini et al., 2022; Lang et al., 2023; Morin et al., 2022; Shendryk, 2022; Tsao et al., 2023).

Recent studies have employed spatial downscaling models to generate wall-to-wall canopy height maps, reducing the spatial resolution of GEDI footprints from 25 m to 10 m and extending their coverage (Di Tommaso et al., 2021; Lahssini et al., 2022; Lang et al., 2023; Li et al., 2020; Potapov et al., 2021; Shendryk, 2022). The majority of these studies calibrate or train their models using GEDI footprints acquired at national or continental (i.e. > 10,000 km²) levels (Lang et al., 2023; Mulverhill et al., 2022; Potapov et al., 2021; Shendryk, 2022). In contrast, few studies focus on calibrating or training their models using local-level GEDI footprints in small geographical extents (i.e. < 10,000 km²) (Schwartz et al., 2022). Local to country scale calibration modeling in complex structural forests can adjust site-specific heterogeneity, such as variations in leaf-on vs. leaf-off forest canopy conditions, reducing the likelihood of pixel-wise underestimation or overestimation of canopy height predictions (Mandl et al., 2023). However, constructing from local to country scale calibrated models for canopy height estimation in intermediate and large extents (i.e. > 10,000 km²) requires intensive computation time or access to a computer cluster due to the size of the geospatial data or methods used (Di Tommaso et al., 2021; Lang et al., 2023; Li et al., 2020; Potapov et al., 2019, 2021; Wang et al., 2022).

To address the computational challenges of satellite data processing, the Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform has emerged as a powerful source for accessing and analyzing petabytes of geospatial remote sensing (RS) data (Gorelick et al., 2017). GEE has revolutionised access

to and analysis of multi-source RS data across various scales, hosting data from different satellite missions and enabling cloud-based data analysis (Francini and Chirici, 2022; Gomes et al., 2020; Gorelick et al., 2017). Leveraging parallel cloud computing processing and diverse programming languages (e.g., JavaScript), GEE efficiently handles vast spatial data (Francini et al., 2021, Francini and Chirici, 2022, 2024; Tamiminia et al., 2020), serving as it invaluable for investigating forestry topics such as forest disturbance analysis, forest health assessment, land cover mapping, and drought monitoring (Francini et al., 2022; Giannetti et al., 2021; Tamiminia et al., 2020). In addition to data access and analysis capabilities, GEE enables the development of web-based apps that facilitate complex analyses of real-time RS data without coding expertise (Scheip and Wegmann, 2021). Recent GEE web apps have been created for various forestry objectives and beyond. For instance, *Global Forest Change* displays global forest change between 2000 and 2022, offering users downloadable tree canopy cover maps (Hansen et al., 2013). *SPECTRAL*, another GEE web app, uses multi-temporal RS data to generate vegetation indices and characterize Earth System dynamics (Montero et al., 2022). *AgKit4EE*, a GEE-enabled toolkit allows for agricultural land-use modeling, which offers functionalities for retrieving, visualizing, and analyzing cropland areas (Zhang et al., 2020). Similarly, *SnowWarp* GEE app provides global daily snow cover data by integrating Landsat and MODIS imagery, supporting effective water resource management and ecosystem monitoring (Laurin et al., 2022). Complementing the functionality of GEE Apps, open-source Python toolkits enhance the replicability of satellite data analyses by offering rapid, automated, and accurate processing, accessible even to users without JavaScript coding expertise. For instance, *CoastSat* facilitates global shoreline change tracking through satellite imagery, offering coastal managers and scientists an efficient tool for monitoring coastlines (Vos et al., 2019). Similarly, *PyVF* automatically detects significant vertical features from high-resolution LiDAR data, enhancing flood modeling by capturing essential topographic details (Gao et al., 2022). Conversely, a hybrid tool named *dataDriven*, which integrates Google Earth Engine and R, enables forest monitoring by producing design-based, data-driven maps of environmental attributes and their precision, using Sentinel-2 imagery as auxiliary data (Francini et al., 2024a).

While GEE offers users access to a wealth of geospatial RS data, fully harnessing its potential generally requires programming and coding skills (Gorelick et al., 2017). However, this challenge can be addressed through collaboration with GEE developer experts, utilizing open-access blog platforms, and exploring artificial intelligence (IA) tools (Yang et al., 2022). Numerous studies have successfully used GEE for processing GEDI products alongside multi-source RS data, with some focusing on mapping canopy heights for a specific area of interest (Di Tommaso et al., 2021; Lang et al., 2023; Mandl et al., 2023; Potapov et al., 2021; Shendryk, 2022; Wang et al., 2022). Despite the availability of global canopy heights as GEE assets, none of the worldwide canopy height maps were fully constructed on the GEE platform at the time of writing (Lang et al., 2023; Mandl et al., 2023; Potapov et al., 2021). This may be attributed to the requirement for advanced GEE coding skills and limited experience on GEE web app development. This hypothesis could elucidate the challenge of producing from local to country scale calibrated height models for extensive areas. One of the main drawbacks of using local server-based platforms for computing intermediate and large geospatial datasets is the significant time investment required for collecting, processing, and modeling maps. For example, the canopy height modeling process could take more than ten days to map global forests (Lang et al., 2023). While this obstacle can be overcome using a computer cluster space, this option may be costly and inaccessible for technicians, forest owners, and the public. Conversely, it is completely feasible to construct a canopy height map calibrated at multiple scale for smaller geographic extents within the GEE ecosystem.

In addition to calibration and processing, several critical factors contribute to the successful prediction of global canopy heights,

including choices about data training (i.e., GEDI relative height – Rh percentiles), data analysis (i.e., spatial downscaling algorithm), and predictors (i.e., environmental factors influencing canopy height growth) (Li et al., 2020; Potapov et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2022). The GEDI instrument collects 3D lidar data without discerning whether data originate explicitly from vegetated areas. This introduces uncertainties in canopy height prediction for forestry studies if GEDI footprints fall within built-up areas or grasslands, GEDI data has been used on non-forest covers to provide valuable insights into vegetation’s health and structural characteristics in ecological and agricultural studies (Di Tommaso et al., 2021). To mitigate uncertainty for canopy height prediction and enhance the assessment of canopy structures, Vangi et al. (2021) suggest adopting a high-resolution forest mask. Additionally, different GEDI Rh metrics, particularly the highest GEDI Rh percentiles (>90th percentile), have been commonly used as a proxy for effectively predicting forest canopy heights due to their capability to penetrate the canopy, especially in denser canopies (Adam et al., 2020; Li et al., 2020;

Potapov et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2022). Ultimately, the input parameters used for canopy height prediction from GEDI data can significantly impact the reliability of canopy height predictions in different vegetation types.

Current global canopy height maps are limited to specific years, may include GEDI footprints outside the AOI, and often incorporate non-forest GEDI footprints in their models. Scalable models may require specific GEDI Rh metrics as proxies for canopy height estimation, which can impact to accurate estimation in certain forest types. Therefore, a tool that allows for the use of GEDI footprints within the AOI, the ability to define the GEDI period, customize the GEDI Rh metric, select robust machine learning models, and apply a forest mask, all without requiring coding knowledge, has become necessary. Considering these requirements, we developed Canopy Height Mapper, a GEE web app (hereafter CH-GEE app) that generates canopy height maps at 10 m spatial resolution by integrating GEDI Rh metrics with multi-source RS data (i.e., radar and optical remote sensing data, and topographical

Fig. 1. Framework illustrating the architecture of the CH-GEE (Canopy Height Mapper Google Earth Engine) application. The backend functions and frontend options enable users to generate high-resolution canopy height maps from a user-defined area of interest (AOI).

ancillary features). GEE web apps offer an ideal platform for developing dynamic, user-friendly, code-free, cost-free, and well-documented methods that leverage the data and computational advantages of GEE. The application uses machine learning (ML) algorithms readily available in GEE (Random Forests, RF; Gradient Tree Boost, GB; Classification And Regression Trees, CART) to construct spatial downscaling models. CH-GEE outputs are validated with Italian NFI field data covering 11,000 km² (Gasparini et al., 2022). This evaluation is based on three key objectives: 1) to compare predicted canopy height maps generated by the CH-GEE app with the reference canopy heights from NFI; 2) to evaluate the relationship between predicted canopy height maps from the CH-GEE app and reference stem volume data (2015) from the NFI; and 3) to investigate the relationship between predicted canopy height maps from the CH-GEE app and reference stem volume data (2023) from the NFI, incorporating annual growth data.

2. Canopy height google earth engine (CH-GEE) app framework

The CH-GEE app is designed as a user-friendly, cost-free and dynamic single-page web application, to enable researchers with varying levels of remote sensing and coding expertise to generate canopy height maps at a 10-m spatial resolution for a specified Area of Interest (AOI; Fig. 1). The approach implemented in CH-GEE has been validated by comparison with other available maps at a local-based level, demonstrating a better fit with ALS-based CHM than the 2019–2020 canopy height GEDI maps (Alvites et al., 2024). The application is built using the web-based Earth Engine code editor, which allows for backend geospatial analysis as well as a frontend user interface (UI) through the Earth Engine JavaScript API. The backend framework relies entirely on the GEE client library and GEE data catalog, harnessing the high-performance computation and data storage capabilities of Google's cloud platform (Gorelick et al., 2017). The primary component of CH-GEE is the backend framework of frequently used functions for data collection and processing, model development and evaluation, and output visualization.

To access the CH-GEE app, users can visit this link: <https://ee-calvites1990.projects.earthengine.app/view/ch-gee>. The link for the CH-GEE codes is https://code.earthengine.google.com/?accept_repo=users/calvites1990/CH-GEE. For the repository and a detailed description of the procedure, the reviewer can refer to this link: <https://github.com/Cesarito2021/CH-GEE.git>. A comprehensive step-by-step guide for using CH-GEE is available in the GitHub repository and supplementary materials. In the CH-GEE app UI, users first need to define the area of interest (by drawing an AOI or uploading an AOI shapefile), select one of

the three forest mask options, choose a GEDI RH metric as a proxy for canopy height, and set the temporal extent for both the GEDI RH metric and Sentinel-1/Sentinel-2. After that, users must define cloud thresholds to manage cloudiness in Sentinel-2. Next, they select one of the three machine learning algorithms, specify the folder path and name for saving the GeoTIFF file to their personal drive, and then click "Run". Finally, users can automatically view the map, scatter plot, and variable importance graphs.

2.1. Data collection and processing

The derived datasets and variables used within the CH-GEE app (Table 1) were selected based on their potential for estimating canopy heights (Matasci et al., 2018; Potapov et al., 2019, 2021; Lang et al., 2023; Mandl et al., 2023). Relative height (Rh) metrics (from 1st to 100th Rh percentiles) measured by each NASA's GEDI footprint (Dubayah et al., 2020) are used as a proxy for canopy height and is the dependent variables to generate wall-to-wall canopy height maps with spatial downscaling models. Sentinel-1 radar, Sentinel-2 optical data, and topographical data (elevation, slope and aspect) are used by the CH-GEE app as independent variables for prediction models. CH-GEE implements radar (Sentinel-1) and optical (Sentinel-2) data to improve prediction accuracy by harnessing the relationships between these data sources and to extrapolate informative biophysical and structural vegetation characteristics. While optical imagery offers insights into the biophysical processes of vegetation, radar data provides complementary information on structural components, surface characteristics, and vegetation moisture content, resulting in a robust data source for classification and prediction purposes (Proietti et al., 2020; Gherboudj et al., 2011; Hird et al., 2017; Van Tricht et al., 2018; Veloso et al., 2017). Furthermore, the CH-GEE app includes topographic features, rather than relying solely on the more common radar and/or optical data. This choice is based on the well-documented influence of topography on vegetation dynamics, which has been recognized as a secondary factor in forest growth, particularly in broadleaf and mixed-species forests (Adrah et al., 2022; Rozenberger and Diaci, 2014). High-quality environmental RS data is essential for accurate modeling and mapping; therefore, all input datasets are preprocessed using a variety of corrections and, filter to ensure high-quality products acquired and processed (Table 1).

2.1.1. Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI)-Level 2 A

The CH-GEE app uses all available GEDI footprints to generate wall-

Table 1

GEE data catalogue sources and related bands used by the CH-GEE app to generate canopy height maps at a 10-m spatial resolution for a specified Area Of Interest (AOI): Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation Level 2 A Geolocated Elevation and Height Metrics Product (GEDI-Level 2 A); Sentinel-1 C-band Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) Ground Range Detected (GRD) data (S1); Harmonized Sentinel-2 Level-2A data (S2); S2 cloud probability (S2-CP), Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data 2010 (GMTED-2010) dataset; Global 4-class PALSAR-2/PALSAR Forest/Non-Forest Map (PALSAR); Dynamic World product (DW). For each product, the temporal coverage (from one year to another year or Up to Date, UTD), the spatial resolution, and the adopted bands for each purpose are displayed.

GEE data catalogue sources					
Product name	GEE ImageCollection ID	Temporal coverage	Spatial resolution	Adopted bands	Usage
GEDI-Level 2 A	LARSE/GEDI/GEDIO2_A_002_MONTHLY	2019- UTD	25 m footprints spaced approximately every 60 m along-track	rh0-100, degrade_flag, quality_flag	Dependent variable quality controls for rh0-100 bands
S1	COPERNICUS/S1_GRD_FLOAT	2014- UTD	10 m 20000 m	VV, VH angle	Independent variables Border noise correction and speckle filtering of S1 bands
S2	COPERNICUS/S2_SR_HARMONIZED	2017- UTD	10–60 m	B1-8, B8A, B9-12	Independent variables
S2-CP	COPERNICUS/S2_CLOUD_PROBABILITY	2015- UTD	10 m	probability	Cloud masking for S2 bands
GMTED-2010	USGS/GMTED2010	2010	231.92 m	be75	Independent variable (elevation, slope and aspect)
PALSAR	JAXA/ALOS/PALSAR/YEARLY/FNF4	2017–2020	25 m	fnf	Forest Mask
DW	GOOGLE/DYNAMICWORLD/V1	2015- UTD	10 m	0, 2–8 and 1	Forest Mask

to-wall canopy height maps using spatial downscaling models. The choice of GEDI Rh metrics has the potential to address the challenges associated with underestimation or overestimation of canopy heights (Potapov et al., 2021; Puletti et al., 2020). Therefore, the CH-GEE app includes all relative height (Rh) metrics (from 1st to 100th Rh percentiles) measured by each NASA's GEDI footprint (Dubayah et al., 2020). Average height metric calculated from the average (AVG) of four GEDI Rh metrics (AVG of 75th, 90th, 95th, and 100th Rh percentiles) is also offered (Alvites et al., 2024). The AVG GEDI Rh metric is incorporated based on a recent study which found that the AVG effectively represents canopy heights, specifically in broadleaf forests (Alvites et al., 2024).

The CH-GEE app filters all Rh metrics using two quality control thresholds: quality and degrade flags. These flags indicate the overall reliability of a waveform in measuring vegetation structure (Hofton et al., 2019; Luthcke et al., 2019), thus waveforms flagged as unsuitable for detecting canopy height measurements are excluded (Quality flag = 1) and only non-degraded laser shots are retained (Degrade flag = 0).

2.1.2. Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2 and topographical data

The Sentinel-1 data originated from a dual-polarization C-band Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) instrument is acquired in both ascending and descending orbits and interferometric wide-swath (IW) mode. This encompasses single (VV and HH) and dual polarization (VH) signals (Dostálová et al., 2021). In the backend framework of the CH-GEE app, Sentinel-1 data is preprocessed with border noise correction, speckle filtering, and radiometric terrain normalization of VV, VH bands (Mullissa et al., 2021).

Sentinel-2 data provides insights on vegetation photosynthetic activities (Kacic et al., 2021, 2023), hence CH-GEE app also includes Sentinel-2 data that comprised 14 bands with spatial resolutions ranging from 10 m to 60 m. To improve the product quality, S2 cloud probability from Sentinel-2 is employed the CH-GEE app for cloud masking, limiting occlusion from opaque and cirrus cloud or highlight reflective surface (e. g., roof tops or snow). The cloud coverage threshold has a direct impact on the accuracy of pixel measurements; excessive cloud cover can augment the bias in predictions by affecting the measurements of wavelengths or bands at the pixel level, which may lead to inaccurate evaluations of forest structure and health (Francini et al., 2024c). A median composite image is then generated from the Sentinel-2 collection (Francini et al., 2022). Additionally, the CH-GEE app integrates DEM data from the Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data (GMTE)-2010 and extracts elevation, slope and aspect (Danielson and Gesch, 2011).

2.1.3. Forest masks

To delineate vegetation in the spatial extent of the study area, the CH-GEE app utilizes two forest masks. The first mask is derived from the Global 4-class PALSAR-2/PALSAR Forest/Non-Forest map (Shimada et al., 2014) and the second mask uses near-real-time Dynamic World product (Brown et al., 2022). The first product, generated using multi-temporal HH and HV polarization images acquired by the Phased Arrayed L-band Synthetic Aperture Radar (PALSAR) instrument aboard the Advanced Land Observing Satellite (ALOS) mission, was validated against images from three independent reference datasets (Google Earth Imagery, the Degree Confluent Project, and the Global Forest Resources Assessment), achieving overall accuracies of 91%, 82%, and 94.81%, respectively (Shimada et al., 2014). It employed a rule-based approach implemented in eCognition software, adhering to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) definition of "forest" (i.e., a natural land area with at least 10% tree cover and a minimum area of 0.5 ha) to classify land cover into four categories: 0 - Dense Forest, 1 - Non-Dense Forest, 2 - Non-Forest, 3 - Water. The CH-GEE app subsequently reclassifies these categories into a binary map (Forest/Non-Forest), merging class 0 with 1 to represent forests and class 2 with 3 to indicate non-forest areas. The second product was generated by integrating near-real-time Sentinel-2 imagery with land-use/land-cover (LULC) data and

ancillary training datasets using a convolutional neural network (CNN) deep learning model implemented in a cloud-based AI platform to classify land use and cover types (Brown et al., 2022). These data were validated against land-use classes from two reference datasets, achieving an overall accuracy of 88.4%. When compared with other LULC datasets in terms of temporal frequency, global coverage, a 73.8% agreement was achieved (Brown et al., 2022). This product classifies land use and cover types into nine categories: 0 - water, 1 - trees, 2 - grass, 3 - flooded vegetation, 4 - crops, 5 - shrub and scrub, 6 - built, 7 - bare, and 8 - snow and ice classes. The CH-GEE app subsequently reclassifies them into a binary map, merging classes 0 and 2-8 to depict non-forest areas while preserving class 1 for forest areas. The resulting mask in the CH-GEE app has a 10-m spatial resolution and is updated in near real-time, with the update frequency varying depending on Sentinel-2 data acquisition (2-5 days).

2.2. Model development and evaluation

Given their proven effectiveness in previous GEDI studies and their ability to analyze extensive geospatial datasets through decision tree analysis (Breiman, 2001; Francini et al., 2023b; Kotsiantis, 2013), the CH-GEE app integrates three ML algorithms: RF (ee.Classifier.smileRandomForest), GB (ee.Classifier.smileGradientTreeBoost), and CART (ee.Classifier.smileCart). All model hyperparameters can be manually adjusted using the configuration panel of the graphical user interface. In the app, random pixels are sampled for each AOI and divided into training (70%) and testing (30%) subsets. The training and testing subsets are used to fit models and evaluate model performance using a cross-validation procedure. The performance of the model's prediction is assessed through root mean squared error (RMSE), expressed in meters (mRMSE) and percentages (pRMSE), as per Eqs. (1) and (2). We selected these metrics as they are standard for evaluating model performance (Lang et al., 2023; Potapov et al., 2021; Alvites et al., 2024), with R-squared indicating the proportion of variance explained by the model (range: 0-1), and RMSE providing a measure of the average prediction error, expressed both in absolute terms (m; mRMSE) and relative terms (%; pRMSE). Additionally, the relationship between predicted (y-axis) and observed data (x-axis) is assessed in the CH-GEE app to determine the extent to which variation in GEDI data is explained by predicted canopy height values, using R-squared and RMSE in a scatter plot. The two statistical measures are calculated using the following formulas, where \hat{y} denotes predicted values of "y", \bar{y} represents reference values of "y," and n indicates sample size:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2} \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

$$R - \text{squared} = \frac{\sum (y_i - \hat{y})^2}{\sum (y_i - \bar{y})^2} \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

The app also visualizes the variable importance of each predictor, providing a bar chart on the frontend.

2.3. Graphical user interface (GUI)

The web-based GUI includes a configuration panel and map explorer. Through the GUI, users can upload a shapefile or manually draw the spatial boundary of the area of interest (AOI). Users can then opt to apply one of two available forest masks to exclude non-forested areas within the AOI. Following spatial delineation, users must select the GEDI Rh metrics, set the temporal extent for GEDI, Sentinel-1 and 2 collections. User-defined parameters generate the mosaic collection for the desired study area to execute one of three available ML algorithms (RF, GB, or CART), with the option to define hyperparameters, following the GEE's instructions (see <https://developers.google.com/earth-engine>

/apidocs). After parameter and model selection in the configuration panel, users can run the app. A resulting canopy height map can be visualized on the map explorer using the WGS84 Coordinate System (EPSG 4326), and subsequently exported to a Google Drive, using an output folder and file name. In addition, predicted vs observed values, variable importance values and their related graphical representations (scatter plot and bar chart) can be plotted and saved as comma-separated values (CSV) files, scalable vector graphics (SVG) or portable network graphic (PNG) images. Further details of the frontend configuration panel and options can be found on the supplementary material – Section 1 and Section 2.

3. Canopy height Mapper (CH-GEE) app in a real-case study

This section showcases a practical implementation of CH-GEE in a real-case forest study. Here, canopy heights maps are generated for twenty Italian regions and validated with forest inventory data.

3.1. Real-case study area

Italian forests comprise 32.5% of the total land area, equivalent to 301,000 km², or approximately 11 million hectares (Fig. 3). Forest coverage varies from 7.4% in Puglia to 63.3% in Liguria. Italy's forests are characterized by high structural complexity and fragmentation (Santopuoli et al., 2016; Vizzarri et al., 2015). There is high diversity of forest types, encompassing 7 of the 11 EU forest types, predominantly represented by broadleaf tree species, which account for 68% of forest cover in Italy (Barbati et al., 2014; Giannetti et al., 2018), most common tree species include European beech, downy oak, Turkey oak, Norway spruce and Black pine (<https://www.inventarioforestale.org/it/>).

The Italian National Forest Inventory (NFI) is a reliable validation

dataset because Italy ranks as the third-largest carbon sink in living trees in the Mediterranean region (641×10^6 Mg) (Bleu, 2018). This significant carbon sequestration capacity is supported by the dynamic patterns observed within these forests: high tree species diversity (~180 woody species), dense crown coverage (74.4% of Italian forests), and structural vertical diversity (ranging from one-layer to multi-layer) (Gasparini et al., 2022). In addition, Italy features a very heterogeneous and complex landscape, which complicates modeling tasks. These characteristics not only highlight the ecological richness of Italian forests but also offer valuable insights into forest management and conservation strategies applicable to broader global contexts. Consequently, we can expect even greater accuracies in other regions of the world, particularly in Mediterranean countries.

3.2. Data

To validate the canopy height maps produced by the CH-GEE app, predicted canopy height was compared with data from the Italian NFI campaign were adopted (Fig. 2). The sampling approach employed for the NFI consists of three phases (Ph.): Ph. 1 involves the classification of land use and land cover via photo-interpretation at over 301,000 points; Ph. 2 includes visiting a subsample of 30,877 points to conduct qualitative measurements; Ph. 3 comprises the collection of quantitative measurements (i.e., canopy height, growing stock, biomass, annual volume increment, deadwood biomass) at approximately 6993 plots, each measuring 530 m² (23 m × 23 m) (Gasparini et al., 2022). Using tree species composition information from plots, we classified each plot into coniferous, broadleaved, and mixed categories. Initially, all trees were assigned to one of the forest types, and subsequently, the dominant forest type (comprising over 80% of trees) was selected for classifying the plot. To determine the plots maximum height, only dominant trees

Fig. 2. Study area in Italy. The figure depicts the national borders of Italy, the forest mask derived from the Global Forest/Non-Forest map (Shimada et al., 2014) the locations of sampled points investigated during the NFI campaign in 2015, and the percentage of forest area covered by region in Italy.

Fig. 3. Canopy height (CH) map of forests for Italian regions. Zoomed-in views highlight two regions with a high percentage of forest cover in the Alps (i.e., Liguria and Trentino-Alto Adige), and two regions with moderate coverage in the Apennines (i.e., Calabria and Molise). The color scale settings of the CH map are consistent with those in the CH-GEE app.

(belonging to the upper layer with heights above the third quantile were used). Subsequently, dominant canopy heights were averaged for each region (e.g. Abruzzo) and each forest type within each region (e.g., coniferous-Abruzzo, broadleaf-Abruzzo, mixed-Abruzzo). These averaged values were used for the validation procedure.

The NFI dataset includes stem volume (m^3/plot) estimates based on allometric equation derived from tree models (Tabacchi et al., 2011). Additionally, the annual volume increment (m^3/plot) is included in the NFI dataset, which was quantified by measuring the width of the five outermost growth rings on cores obtained from each plot (Gasparini et al., 2022). We calculated the 2023 stem volume by adding the sum of the past eight years' annual stem volume increments to the 2015 stem volume.

3.3. Methods

We used the CH-GEE app to generate and validate canopy height maps on a region-by-region and forest-site basis. The spatial extent of the study areas was defined using the “Global Forest/Non-Forest” forest mask derived from the PALSAR – ALOS mission (Shimada et al., 2014).

GEDI Rh metric, the setting of the temporal extent of radar and optical data, their quality and the machine learning algorithm were also set. Following Alvites et al. (2024), we selected the average GEDI Rh metric (AVG metric) as a proxy for canopy height prediction, given that approximately 68% of the Italian landscape is covered by broadleaf forests. All multi-temporal radar and optical data (<70% cloud coverage) available in GEE between July 1st and August 31st, 2023, were included in the analysis, along with topographical data.

To train robust spatial downscaling models, RF was chosen, as it was successfully employed in developing a global canopy height map (Potapov et al., 2021) and outperformed GB and CART algorithms (Alvites et al., 2024). Moreover, the RF has been widely used in remote sensing due to its ability to handle high-dimensional data, reduced sensitivity to overfitting, facilitation of rapid and complex bagging analyses, and generation of highly accurate predictions (Belgiu and Drăguț, 2016). Using the training dataset, corresponding to 70% of the selected random pixels, the best RF model was performed using the ee.Classifier.smileRandomForest GEE tool, with the only hyperparameter configured being “ntrees” which was set to 500 in the CH-GEE app, while all other hyperparameters were left at their default settings. The

downscaling model converts coarse GEDI footprint (~ 25 m) layers into finer 10 m resolution, ensuring multiple pixels within one footprint. These 10 m layers are used to build optimal RF models, which predict canopy heights across the entire AOI using a spatializing approach.

To validate the accuracy of the predicted canopy height map on a region-by-region and forest-site basis, we evaluated of model prediction performance, using R-squared, mRMSE, and pRMSE automatically generated by the CH-GEE app. We then determined the relationship between predicted canopy heights and reference data (canopy height data; stem volume data of 2015 and 2023) derived from NFI campaign using a linear regression analysis. To explore potential sources of discrepancy, we removed influential outliers on models using Cook’s distance approach (Cook, 1977) before the analyses. The R-squared with p-value, and RMSE values, following formulas in Eqs. (1) and (2) were used.

All validation analyses were implemented in R software, using “stats” (R Core Team, 2023), the “tidyverse” R package (Wickham et al., 2019) and the “terra” R package (Hijmans, 2023).

4. Results

4.1. Model performance

The CH-GEE app generated high-resolution forest canopy height maps at a 10-m resolution for all 20 Italian regions (Fig. 3). These maps revealed that tallest canopies were primarily located in northern Italy, in Trentino-Alto Adige, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, and Liguria (Fig. 4). Additionally, the results from the CH-GEE app indicated similar canopy heights in the central and southern Apennine regions, including Calabria and Molise. Contrasting patterns of RMSE results were observed across the regions, ranging from 33.75% ($r = 0.82$; Trentino Alto-Adige) to 54.28% ($r = 0.79$; Toscana) (Fig. 4).

4.2. Comparison of predicted canopy heights map with reference canopy heights from NFI campaign

The CH-GEE app successfully generated canopy heights that closely matched the reference canopy height from the 2015 NFI campaign, with RMSE ranging from 17% to 19% (Fig. 5).

When comparing the predicted canopy heights to the ground-truth

Fig. 4. Map accuracy results displaying the coefficient of correlation (r), root mean squared error (pRMSE, %), and forest area cover (%). The surface areas exclude the “other wooded land” category (Gasparini et al., 2022).

Fig. 5. Scatter plots comparing predicted with reference canopy heights obtained by regions. Reference canopy heights were measured during the Italian National Forest Inventory (NFI) campaign in 2015.

measurements, all regions exhibited a similar response pattern in models considering or excluding outliers, with pRMSE values ranging from 14% to 36% in models excluding outliers (Fig. 6). Notably, models excluding outliers achieved a more pronounced accuracy for broadleaf trees (R-squared = 0.59 & pRMSE = 14%) and mixed trees (R-squared = 0.77 & pRMSE = 26%).

4.3. Relationship between predicted canopy heights map and reference stem volume from NFI

When the relationship between predicted canopy heights and stem volume data of 2015 and 2023 years, the predicted values demonstrated consistent explanatory power across both years, with R-squared values ranging from 0.82 to 0.83 (Fig. 7). The predicted values obtained from the CH-GEE app better explain the variability of stem volume for broadleaf forests in 2023 (R-squared = 0.57) compared to 2015 (R-

Fig. 6. Scatter plots comparing predicted canopy heights with reference measurements based on the predominant forest type. Reference canopy heights were measured during the Italian National Forest Inventory (NFI) campaign in 2015.

squared = 0.54). Conversely, prediction in coniferous and mixed forests exhibited similar explanatory power across both years (R^2 -squared values in supplementary material Section 3).

5. Discussion

Wall-to-wall canopy height data have not been provided as part of GEDI products. Here, we present a novel method to generate canopy height maps for a specific AOI through a code-free, cost-free, user-friendly app. We introduce the CH-GEE app, a dynamic GEE web application built on the GEE platform, which integrates GEDI footprints with multi-source remote sensing data to map canopy heights at local- and regional-levels worldwide. The GEE platform enables access to and analysis of vast amounts of geospatial data without the need for local high-performance computing. It eliminates the requirement for large disk space to store multi-temporal images, simplifies the execution and development of machine learning functions, and supports users with well-documented instructional materials (Francini et al., 2022; Gomes

et al., 2020; Gorelick et al., 2017).

The CH-GEE app harnesses the benefits of the cloud-based infrastructure of GEE. It enables the construction of local-to-country scale calibrated models selecting GEDI footprints, choosing Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 time windows, and selecting specific algorithms. These features are invaluable for addressing common issues such as removing cloud cover, selecting optimal phenological periods. Additionally, the app facilitates robust model constructions through hyperparameter calibration. GEE offers substantial benefits for geo-big data analytics, including enhanced accessibility and cost-effectiveness through its flexible processing, memory, and storage options. With an analysis-ready data catalogue of approximately 90 petabytes, GEE facilitates parallel processing of extensive datasets, significantly improving the efficiency of large-scale data analysis (Gorelick et al., 2017). In our study, each of the 20 canopy height region maps (.TIFF) was generated in under 1 min. The file sizes for these maps ranged from 32.2 MB (Valle D'Aosta) to 241 MB (Piemonte), with transfer times to a personal drive varying from 2 to 30 min. Additionally, the CH-GEE app required less

Fig. 7. Scatter plots comparing predicted canopy heights with reference stem volume for 2015 and 2023. Reference data were obtained from Italian National Forest Inventory (NFI) campaign.

than 2 min to download the output map. Conversely, the main limitation of the CH-GEE is its restricted mapping area, which is currently confined to the GEDI footprint zone (between 52° N and 52° S of latitude).

5.1. Model performance

Evaluation across all twenty regions revealed that the R-squared and RMSE for canopy height estimates obtained by CH-GEE app fell within a comparable range to those of other regional canopy height maps in the set-aside data, ranging between 3.4 m and 8.9 m. These errors were slightly smaller than those obtained by global canopy height maps (i.e. 9.6 m in Potapov et al., 2021; Mandl et al., 2023; Shendryk, 2022; Wang et al., 2022). These findings align with those of Potapov et al. (2021), who noted that national and regional canopy height maps tend to be more accurate than global ones.

The RF model within CH-GEE allowed us to address canopy-related prediction challenges across various forest sites, achieving an overall accuracy of 17% pRMSE ($R\text{-squared} = 0.89$). When compared our predictions to reference ground-truth data, the accuracy achieved was higher than that demonstrated in other canopy height maps (Lang et al., 2023; Potapov et al., 2021; Silveira et al., 2023). When compared the predicted values with the reference canopy heights from NFI, we observed more accurate accuracy in broadleaf (pRMSE = 14%) and mixed trees (pRMSE = 26%) than coniferous (pRMSE = 36%). There are numerous challenges associated with validating RS predictions with ground-truth data (Chi et al., 2016; Kellner et al., 2023; Tomppo et al., 2008). However, the predicted height accuracy of CH-GEE compared with NFI data surpassed the accuracy compared with ALS data (Li et al., 2020; Potapov et al., 2021). Furthermore, we found that accuracy

improved when comparing predicted canopy heights from the CH-GEE app with stem volume of 2023 compared to 2015 data in broadleaf sites (dominant forest sites in Italy). This indicates that recent ground-truth data is essential for reliably assessing predicted canopy height maps. While monitoring stem volume using canopy height remains challenging, the CH-GEE outputs align with those obtained in another study that using high-resolution PlanetScope imagery data as a predictor instead of Sentinel (Liu et al., 2023). The agreement between predicted and reference canopy heights may be influenced by the gap of over four years between the launch of GEDI's NASA mission and the conclusion of the NFI survey campaign in 2015. Furthermore, the NFI monitoring had a long-term interval ranging from 5 to 10 years (Francini et al. 2022a). During this time difference, there many have been significant changes to vegetation vertical structure (Francini and Chirici, 2022). Several secondary factors could have adversely impacted the agreement between predicted and reference canopy heights, including tree morphology (Puletti et al., 2020), tree composition (pure vs. mixed forests), stand structure (homogeneous vs. heterogeneous), topographical conditions (Adam et al., 2020), time windows for Sentinel data (2023 were assumed to be a cloudy year in Italy, thereby limiting the available images for map development) (Francini et al., 2022), GEDI geolocation (Roy et al., 2021), and sampling NFI points at regionals and forest site levels. This latter factor is supported by the number and distribution of plots monitored in NFI, where, for example, 67% corresponded to broadleaf (4621 plots), 14.6% to coniferous (1005 plots), 17.8% to mixed (1227 plots), and 0.58% to shrub (40 plots). Notably, the CH-GEE integrates a global DEM to mitigate topographic uncertainty. Additionally, GEDI geolocation uncertainty remains a well-known source of error, warranting further investigation for the

second version of GEDI (Roy et al., 2021).

Our results indicate that canopy heights under 30 m, which represent the majority of Italian trees (see Fig. 5), tended to be slightly overestimated in most Italian regions. However, we attribute this uncertainty primarily to the heterogeneity of investigated forest sites (see Fig. 6). A similar pattern of overestimation was also observed in a canopy height map using a robust deep learning algorithm (Lang et al., 2023). Future studies should compare deep learning and other machine learning approaches to improve canopy height estimates worldwide, particularly in areas where GEDI footprints are available. Deep learning is currently not freely available on the GEE platform and is typically implemented on local server-based systems, which entail computational and technical costs (Abiodun et al., 2018; Lang et al., 2023). However, RF predictions align well with ground-truth canopy heights derived from national inventories conducted in previous years. Although we adopt ground-truth data of dominant trees (third quartile), excluding trees of the intermediate and lowest layers, our findings are consistent with those previously observed for shorter vegetation (<5 m) (Tsao et al., 2023), highlighting the adaptability of the CH-GEE app for investigating vegetation across different ecosystems (Di Tommaso et al., 2021; Tsao et al., 2023).

Broadleaf forests yielded the highest accuracy among the observed forest types, largely due to the extensive coverage of broadleaf forests in Italy, where broadleaf species constitute over half of the species (Gasparini et al., 2022). This finding underscores the significance of employing numerous training samples within the area of interest to train robust local machine learning models. In other national and regional studies, the accuracy of maps has significantly improved because the selected training data more accurately reflects the area to be downscaled (Mandl et al., 2023; Tsao et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2022). However, it is important to note that studies employ definitions and measurement protocols that differ from the Italian NFI protocol. Global maps aim to predict the canopy height of as much vegetation (usually forests) as possible. This inevitably involves trade-offs such as averaging the impact of local biodiversity (e.g., taxonomical, and functional diversity) or variations in topography. For instance, when global models are optimized for taller trees, they may sacrifice predictability in shrublands and plantations (Tsao et al., 2023).

Interestingly, coniferous, and mixed forests exhibited lower prediction accuracy than broadleaf ones when we compared the predicted CH-GEE map with NFI canopy heights (Fig. 6). Lower accuracy has been found for heterogeneous forest types in numerous GEDI and ICESat downscaling studies (Da Conceição Bispo et al., 2023; Sothe et al., 2022). Here, we found relatively low accuracy values in homogenous areas, such as coniferous forests. The heterogeneity also depends on the decentralized setting of the Italian context and forest fragmentation, particularly the owner's regime (Santopuoli et al., 2019; Alvites et al., 2021). Moreover, this could be attributed to several factors related to forest disturbance that have occurred since the sampling date of NFI (i.e., 2015; time for measuring 5–10 years). In recent years, the Italian forest has experienced numerous disturbances. For instance, windstorms in recent years have affected several Italian regions, including Trentino Alto Adige, Veneto, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Lombardia, Piemonte, and Valle d'Aosta (Chirici et al., 2019). A study revealed that the VAIA windstorm destroyed approximately 67,000 km² of forest, predominantly coniferous, in the Italian Alps (Giannetti et al., 2021). Additionally, pest disturbances caused by the spruce bark beetle were detected in Veneto and Friuli-Venezia Giulia (Bozzini et al., 2023) and Trentino-Alto Adige (Dalponte et al., 2023).

Based on the CH-GEE app's performance, its configuration can ensure accurate canopy height estimations, effective monitoring of seasonal changes, and tailored analyses for diverse ecological and agricultural applications. The ability of CH-GEE to select GEDI footprints and predictors for specific time periods enables detailed

monitoring of canopy changes. Predictors calculated over summer have proven to provide the best results, especially in broadleaf trees (Francini et al., 2024c). Users can define areas of interest in crop zones to track growth dynamics during critical growing seasons. These capabilities pose the CH-GEE app as a valuable tool for ecological and agricultural monitoring with significant potential for broader applications globally.

5.2. Further applications and operational uses

As demonstrated in this study, the CH-GEE app allows researchers to dynamically access RS canopy heights at a finer spatial scale. This capability extends not only to tall, forested areas, which store the majority of global carbon, but also to vegetation outside forests that significantly contribute to carbon budgets across (Bazzato et al., 2021a, 2022; Da Conceição Bispo et al., 2023; Skole et al., 2021).

In an operational setting, the app's flexibility, including the option to select up to 100 Rh values, enables the monitoring of various vegetation layers, ranging from forest canopies to regrowth and crops (Lang et al., 2023; Potapov et al., 2021; Di Tommaso et al., 2021). This adaptability makes CH-GEE highly relevant for forestry and agricultural applications such as tracking shrub dynamics, assessing biodiversity, health, and supporting restoration efforts, as demonstrated by studies that leverage relative canopy height data for ecological and agricultural applications (Di Tommaso et al., 2021; Landmann et al., 2023; Dalagnol et al., 2021). Moreover, high-resolution canopy height data are key source for monitoring biodiversity patterns. Recent studies demonstrated that canopy structural heterogeneity indices derived from space are valuable for assessing forest diversity from small to large areas (Duncanson et al., 2023; Torresani et al., 2023). These findings are consistent with the hypothesis that the CH-GEE app can support real-time decision-making in forest management, biodiversity conservation, and agriculture by enabling regular monitoring of tree growth, forest disturbances, and carbon sequestration. The map of the CH-GEE app, when combined with other spatial datasets, offers a practical solution for monitoring tree mortality, canopy gaps, and vegetation dynamics at both local and regional scales. In addition, CH-GEE app could be a valuable tool for monitoring canopies in boreal, temperate, subtropical, and tropical primary forests, as well as savannas and urban forests (Francini et al., 2024b; Schneider et al., 2020).

The current version of the CH-GEE app allows users to directly define GEDI footprint periods for mapping. This functionality enhances its applicability for monitoring changes over time and strengthens its use in both research and operational contexts, such as forest disturbance analysis, management, and ecological monitoring. Additionally, our canopy height map, when integrated with other available maps (Lang et al., 2023; Potapov et al., 2021), can still facilitate the monitoring of tree growth dynamics in hotspot areas (Parra and Simard, 2023) and assess the influence of disturbance events on canopy structures in humid tropical ecosystems (Hansen et al., 2019). Furthermore, periodically producing canopy height maps is crucial with flexible and periodic calibrations for identifying anthropogenic or ecological shifts in vegetation structure for adequate vegetation monitoring in both natural forested areas (Kacic et al., 2023) and fragmented areas (Bazzato et al., 2021b).

Based on findings obtained in Italian forests, which are characterized by approximately 180 species and vertical strata ranging from one-layer to multi-layer, the CH-GEE app is a robust tool for accurately describing canopy heights in structurally complex forests, particularly those with high species diversity. The hypothesis is that mature to old-growth forests, which sequester substantial amounts of carbon (Bono et al., 2024), can benefit from integrating inventories with the CH-GEE app to effectively monitor carbon stocks and other climate-smart forestry indicators (Alfieri et al., 2024).

Future research should prioritize validating canopy height estimations using a global NFI dataset to enhance the CH-GEE app. Additionally, addressing the scalability limit of 25,000 km² (largest Italian region) requires upgrading the GEE account to a business plan for broader applicability. Incorporating key vegetation indices and utilizing finer Digital Elevation Model (DEM) resolutions will further improve model accuracy. Identifying optimal months for monitoring global forests and integrating comparisons to CHM ALS will be crucial for evaluating potential errors in height estimations. Furthermore, investigating how error rates may vary in taller trees or complex forest structures will provide valuable insights for refining the model. These advancements will enhance the CH-GEE app's functionality and utility in ecological and biodiversity assessments.

6. Conclusions

This study introduces and evaluates the CH-GEE, an application that generates high-resolution canopy height maps for global forest ecosystems by integrating NASA's GEDI data with multi-source data through machine learning algorithms. Accessible at the link <https://ee-calvites1990.projects.earthengine.app/view/ch-gee>, the CH-GEE app is user-friendly and freely available. It represents a promising tool for assessing forest carbon storage, biodiversity, and disturbance.

The CH-GEE app produces from local to country scale calibrated canopy height maps (i.e., at local and regional levels) for almost all of Earth's forests, covering a global range between 51.6° N and 51.6° S of latitude. The app currently supports monitoring areas up to a maximum of 25,000 km². To overcome this limitation, users can upgrade their GEE account to a commercial plan. The app's predictive capabilities underscore its potential for assisting NFI survey campaigns, reducing operational costs of forestry measurements, and identifying areas of interest within forests. With its ability to monitor diverse ecosystems, including tropical, temperate, boreal, savannas, and even urban forests, CH-GEE app holds promise for a wide range of applications. By allowing users to configure data collection periods for Sentinel data imagery, CH-GEE app enables repeat analyses across various intervals, mitigating the impact of adverse weather conditions and phenological phases across different geographical areas. This feature enhances the app's utility in investigating forest disturbance and growth dynamics, contributing significantly to assessments of sustainable forest management and climate change mitigation efforts. While the maps generated by the CH-GEE app show promising alignment with Italian National Forest Inventory data, further validation using reference data collected during periods of NASA's GEDI instrument operation is warranted. Nonetheless, the real-time, code-free access to GEDI data offered by CH-GEE app, coupled with its dynamic configuration options, makes it a valuable tool for monitoring canopy heights from local to country scale.

Further research efforts should focus on enhancing the accuracy of models across diverse forest ecosystems, leveraging canopy height datasets from different regions to improve model calibration and performance.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Cesar Alvites: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Hannah O'Sullivan:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Saverio Francini:** Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Marco Marchetti:** Writing – review & editing. **Giovanni Santopuoli:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Gherardo Chirici:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Bruno Lasserre:** Writing – review & editing. **Michela Marignani:** Writing – review & editing. **Erika Bazzato:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Software availability

Name of the software: Canopy Height Mapper (name abbreviated CH-GEE).

Developer: Cesar Alvites [aut, cre], Hannah O'Sullivan [aut], Saverio Francini [ctb], Erika Bazzato [aut, cre].

Contact information: calvites1990@gmail.com.

Year first available: 2024.

Program language: Java language in Google Earth Engine (GEE).

Cost: free;

Software availability: <https://ee-calvites1990.projects.earthengine.app/view/ch-gee> (last stable version GEE App); https://code.earthengine.google.com/?accept_repo=users/calvites1990/CH-GEE (last stable version GEE code); <https://github.com/Cesarito2021/CH-GEE.git> (development version).

Software Tutorial: The tutorial of the Canopy Height Mapper Google Earth Engine is at <https://github.com/Cesarito2021/CH-GEE.git>.

Size of archive: <https://github.com/Cesarito2021/CH-GEE/tree/main/CH-GEE/Code>: 90 KB.

Note: The data used in this application include GEDI (Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation), Sentinel-1, Sentinel-2, and topographical features from the Global Multi-resolution Terrain Elevation Data (GMTED)-2010, all of which are available in the Google Earth Engine cloud-based catalogue. The downscaling and spatialization of canopy heights can be performed using the Canopy Height Mapper Google Earth Engine app.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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enze.wordpress.com/).

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2024.106268>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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